

PHYTONYMS IN THE WORK "MAHBUB UL-QULUB".

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Abstract. In this article, the plant names used in the works of Alisher Navoi belong to which language (geneology), i.e. several words are used to name the same plant, words expressing new concepts are created on the basis of phytonyms, "Mahbub ul "-qulub" is used to study lexemes with the word "plant" divided into lexical-semantic groups.

Key words: samar, fākiha, šajar, bāgāt, čečak, savsan, tukhm, opium, dāna, pāliz, karam, tarra, nargis, yīgač, nakhl, bār, fākiha, kamgaq, nabāt

Plant names form a certain layer in each vernacular language. The names of the plants reflect the scale of the flora and fauna corresponding to the historical-geographical region and climate where this people lived.

Researcher M.Usmonova writes about phytonyms in the thinker's works: It was found that there are more than 300 words related to plants used by Alisher Navoi in the language of Alisher Navoi's works. They are names of fruit and non-fruit trees and their fruits, names of flowers, vegetables, grasses and related words. In terms of which language (ie geneological) the names of plants used in the works of Alisher Navoi belong to, our study gave the following results: common Turkic and Uzbek words - 34, Arabic words - 53, Persian - Tajik words - 204. In addition, it was noted that there are 14 words with mixed Arabic-Persian and Persian-Turkish content.

The language founded by Alisher Navoi is a highly artistic language that combines the language features of various Turkic clans and tribes, adopted words from other languages due to historical-geographical, socio-political conditions. Such wealth is

reflected in the vocabulary of the poet's works, especially in the lexical fund belonging to the world of plants. That is, several words were used to name the same plant, words representing new concepts were created on the basis of phytonyms.

It is appropriate to study the lexemes with the word "plant" used in "Mahbub ul-Qulub" into the following lexical-semantic groups:

1. Tree names: meva, samar- "fruit"; samara - "fruit", bar - "fruit", fākiha - "fruit", tree, yığaç, šajar - "tree", ašjar - "trees", leaf, leaf, pomegranate, pistachio, grape, cypress, tall, sycamore.
2. Flower names: čaman, bāg, bāgāt, ravza, bostān, čečäk, gul, nargis, gunča, lāla, nilufar, savsan, saman.
3. Names of grain crops: crop, mazra - "field", root, seed, grain, wheat, tariq, barley, opium - "poppy", bağ - "cannabis",
4. Names of vegetables: sabza, pāliz, rayhān, karam, tarra - "vegetables".

It is known that, unlike other words, the concept of "bush", "fruit", and "flower" of this plant is expressed in the name of a plant. It is understood from the speech unit (context) that it means "bush" or "fruit" or "flower". For example, in the language of Navoi's works, flower is not the only word with this meaning, the meaning of "flower" is also represented by the common Turkic word čečäk: Kuyaš bilä abri bahārdek kara tufrağdīn gular ačar (MQ,10); Yafrağnī is made of silk, and chečäk leaf is bāl (MQ,77). Čečäk is first found in Yusuf Khos Hajib's epic "Kutadgu Bilig", and the use of flower (DTS, 195) is first found in Ahmed Yugnaki's "Hibatul Haqayyk": the roe deer plays on the pox - the wild goat and the horses play on the pox. ynar (DTS,143). Also, in the source taken as an object, the grammatical plural of flower ("flowers") is Turkish çaman (MQ,29), Arabic ağlāl (MQ,28), Persian-Tajik gulistān (MQ,6), gulšan (MQ ,44), bostān (MQ,7) terms are also used.

In the language of the work "Mahbubu ul-Qulub" there are several words that represent the types of flowers. All of them turned out to be Persian-Tajik words.

1. The word *Lāla*, as in the modern Uzbek language, represented a type of flower:
Yel āgārči lāla tājīn učurğay (MQ,62)

Pista is the Persian name of the fruit; this word is Arabic *fustuq*//*fustak*. From the beginning of the 14th century, the word *pistachio* appears in written records. The word *pistachio* has been adopted into other languages in different forms. Some researchers connect this word to the original Greek and call it from the Greek *pissa*, *pitta* (resin), while others connect it with the Persian *piste*, *pista*. In our opinion, the international Latin name of this word *piste* is derived from Persian. The word *pistachio* is used a lot in Navoi's works.

The Persian-Tajik word *meva* in modern Uzbek is found in the poet's works, but several other words are also used for the meaning of this word:

In the work "*Mahbub ul-Qulub*" the meaning of "tree fruit, harvest" is expressed by several phytonyms:

Persian-Tajik *meva*: And this sweet *meva walāyat bāği šajarasīdīn bolğay* (MQ,49).

It can be found out from the work "*Golden light*" dated to the 10th century that this *sema* was sung through the word *sema yemiš* in ancient times: ...*bimba atliğ yemiš teg* - like a fruit called *bimba* (DTS, 255).

Persian-Tajik *bār* - "fruit, harvest": ... *dānāsi durri saādat bār bergāy va tuxm sačīb, anjumī uluvvi rifat tergāy* (MQ, 29).

Persian-Tajik *fākiha* - "fruit, harvest": ... this delicious *fākiha hidāyat šajarasīn samarasī bolğay* (MQ,49).

Arabic *samar* - "fruit, harvest": *Sakhavat insāniyat bāğīniñ barvar šajarīdur, but ul šajarniñ mufid samarīdur* (MQ,59). This word also has the meaning of "result, benefit": ... *шохоӣ istiğnā va hurmut samar kelturūr* (MQ, 59).

Arabic *samara* - "fruit, harvest": ...*hidāyat šajarasīn samarasī bolğay* (MQ,49).

In Navoi's works, there are words that denote the concepts of seed, grain, ear of crops and the units that collectively name the world of plants. This can also be seen in the language of the work under study:

Qamğaq means "plant" (instead of a common name): Ease fartīdīn barbād erür qamğaq yafrāğī (MQ,62).

Nabāt means "herb, herb": This plant is used for snack (MQ, 13).

Dāna means "seed, grain": Farming, dāna saçar, rizq yolın açar by plowing the earth (MQ, 29). This phytonym means "tooth grain" in the figurative sense: ...başı köksigä tüşüb, ağzı huqqasīdīn dānallari pelilüb (MQ,86).

Tukhm means "plant seed": ...dānāsi durri saādat bār bergäy va tukhm sačīb, anjumī uluvvi rifat tergäy (MQ,29). This word is also used in the meanings of "seed of goodness", "seed of offspring, generation": Yakhšīliq tukhmin sačğilkīm, budu dehqānğa söz (MQ,83); ...this is the drying of the eggs of the offspring of one of them (MQ,90).

In the language of Alisher Navoi's works, the names of flowers, fruitless and fruitless trees, vegetables, among other words, are lexemes used according to the content and artistic requirements of poetic and prose works. Therefore, in addition to their terminological meaning (being a name), such phytonyms also served to express portable meanings as universal words.

There is a peculiarity in the semantics of the names of fruit trees: the name of a fruit tree means the meaning of the fruit tree itself, the meaning of its fruit, and the meaning of its body (wood). These three meanings cannot be called portable meanings, because one did not grow out of the other; they cannot be synonymous words, because they are not words that show different aspects of the same concept.

Conditional abbreviations

DTS - Drevnetyurksky dictionary. -L.: Nauka, 1969. -676 p.

ESTONIA – 1) Sevortyan E. Etymological dictionary of Turkish language. Obshchetyurkskie and mejtyurkskie osnovy na glasnye. -M.: Nauka, 1974. -767 p.

MQ - Mahmud Kashgari. Devonu dictionary turk / Translator and publisher S.M. Mutallibov. I-III. - T.: Science, 1960-1963.

MQ - Navoi. Mahbub ul-kulub. A perfect collection of works. Twenty roofs. Fourteenth roof. - Tashkent: Science. 1998.

OTIL is an explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. I-V. - T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2006-2008.

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